

IMPROVEMENT OF DAMPING PROPERTY OF CFRP COMPOSITE BEAM INTERLEAVED WITH SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER BY USING CFRP LAMINATE AS A HEATER

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SUMMARY: In the present paper, the damping properties of a carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) and glass fiber reinforced plastic (GFRP) hybrid composite laminate are controlled by CFRP laminate itself as a heater in order to construct so-called smart structures. An shape memory polymer (SMP) film is interleaved between the CF/GF hybrid laminate as a damping material and heated at the desirable temperature. From the preliminary experiments, it is found that the heating capability of the CFRP laminate heater is enough to control the temperature of the composite specimen. It is also verified that the surface temperature is almost uniformly distributed in overall specimen. The damping properties of the composite beam including SMP are analyzed by the Ross-Kerwin-Unger analysis.

KEYWORDS: CF/GF hybrid laminate, damping control, sandwich composite beam, shape memory polymer, CFRP heater, free vibration test, smart materials, Ross-Kerwin-Unger analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) have excellent specific strength and specific modulus. Therefore, FRP are widely used for machines and constructions which require light weight. FRP are not only light weighted materials, but also tailor made materials.

Recently, numerous studies of constructing smart materials and structures prosper as one of methods which produces more high performance materials. The smart materials and structures have sensors and actuators to adapt themselves to environment and control their properties. FRP consists of two or more materials. This property is suitable for embedding sensors or actuators in its molding process. The idea of constructing smart materials and structures matches with such a concept for the idea of composite materials that the properties of composite materials can be tailored by combining with materials having different properties.

The damping property is one of important factors for improving the fatigue life of materials and structures. CFRP laminates have excellent specific strength and specific modulus, but their damping property laminate is not so high. There are some methods for improving damping property of CFRP laminate. One of methods is adding visco-elastic materials to CFRP laminate. There are two techniques to add the visco-elastic layers. One is attaching the visco-elastic layers to the surface of the composite laminates, so called free visco-elastic layers, and another is to interleave visco-elastic layers between the composite laminates, so called constrained visco-elastic layers [1],[2]. The former is easier to construct them, while the latter is more effective to improve the damping properties of them. In the present paper, the latter technique is adopted and an SMP film is interleaved as a visco-elastic layer. The SMP is very sensitive to the temperature. Especially, near glass transition temperature (T_g) the visco-elastic properties of the SMP have a large change. The dynamic properties of the composite beam have strong dependency of the visco-elastic properties of sandwiched visco-elastic layer. It is expected that the composite beams having various dynamic properties are produced by controlling the temperature of the SMP.

The temperature of the composite beam is influenced by the change of the environment temperature [3],[4],[5]. A carbon fiber is not only a strong material, but also an electrically conductive material. Therefore, in order to make the composite beam smart, CFRP layers are utilized for controlling the temperature of specimen as a heater. Since CFRP has strong anisotropy in electric resistance, CFRP laminate having $\pm 45^\circ$ fiber orientation was adopted.

The damping property of the composite beam is measured under clamped-free condition as changing the temperature of the composite beam by using CFRP laminate as the heater. The damping property of the composite beam is also calculated by Ross-Kerwin-Ungar analysis. The calculated values showed good agreement with the experimental values.

SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER

Visco-elastic properties of SMP are extremely changed above and below the T_g . In this paper, this characteristics are utilized for improving damping properties of the composite beam. A polyurethane based SMP is adopted. The complex shear moduli and the loss tangent of the SMP are shown in Fig. 1. In this figure, G' and G'' are the storage shear modulus and the loss shear modulus, respectively and $\tan \delta$ means the loss tangent. The T_g is about 45°C . It is found that this SMP change the maximum elasticity at T_g .

SPECIMEN

The composite beam specimen consists of 9 layers as shown in Fig. 2. The fiber orientation of the composite beam is $[0^\circ\text{GF}/+45^\circ\text{CF}/-45^\circ\text{CF}/0^\circ\text{GF}/\text{SMP}/0^\circ\text{GF}/-45^\circ\text{CF}/+45^\circ\text{CF}/0^\circ\text{GF}]$, where CF and GF mean carbon fiber and glass fiber prepreps, respectively. Since CFRP is an electric conductive material, CFRP layers in such a beam are also used as a heater to increase the temperature of the composite beam. But, there are some problems for utilize CFRP laminates as the heater.

Fig 1: Visco-elastic property of shape memory polymer

Fig 2: Schematic view of composite beam specimen with stacking sequence of CF and GF prepregs

INFLUENCE OF FIBER ORIENTATION ON THERMAL CHARACTERISTICS OF CFRP LAMINATE

Two kinds of CFRP laminates having fiber orientations $[0^\circ]$ and $[\pm 45^\circ]$ are prepared and tested. A specimen having $[0^\circ]$ fiber orientation was not uniformly heated when applied the electric voltage by an electric D.C. power supply. The temperature at the free end of the specimen was much higher than the temperature at other parts of specimen. This

phenomenon is explained by Ohm law. The generation of heat per unit area is related to the electric resistance and the electric voltage. That is, the generation of heat per unit area is in proportion to the electric resistance per area of the specimen. In the carbon fiber direction, the electric conduction is caused by carbon fibers which may role as a conductive wire. On the other hand, it is mainly caused by the contact of the carbon fibers in the perpendicular direction to the carbon fibers. Therefore, the lack of uniformity in heating was observed at the top end of CFRP [0°] laminate. Based on such an idea that the CFRP [$\pm 45^\circ$] laminate which has isotropy in electric resistance, the specimen using CFRP [$\pm 45^\circ$] laminate is adopted. In this case, the uniform heat of generation was observed in overall specimen.

THERMAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE BEAM

In order to examine the thermal capability of CFRP laminate as a heater, the heating test is conducted at the room temperature. The specimen is supported under the clamped-free condition and the electric power is supplied to the fixed end of the CFRP laminate by the D.C. power supply. The temperature on the surface of the specimen is measured by a thermocouple. The relation between the temperature on the surface of the specimen and the electric voltage supplied to the CFRP laminate is shown in Fig. 3. In this figure, it is known that each saturated temperature is increased as increasing applied electric voltages. The heating changes of the specimen are shown in Fig. 4. The specimen is heated faster as increasing applied electric voltages. In this experiment the maximum voltage applied to the CFRP heater was 24V due to the restriction of the experimental system.

Fig 3: Temperature on the surface of composite beam specimen and electric voltage supplied to CFRP heater

Fig 4: Temperature changes of composite beam specimen with various electric voltages supplied to CFRP heater

DAMPING PROPERTIES OF CFRP COMPOSITE BEAM

Experiments by using CFRP heater

The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 5. It consists of a composite beam specimen supported under the clamped-free condition, a non-contacting laser pick-up, an FFT analyzer, a D.C. power supply and an impulse hammer. The experiment was performed by the free vibration test. The impulse input at the free end of the specimen is given by the impulse hammer. The response at the free end of the specimen is measured by the non-contacting laser pick-up and recorded by the FFT analyzer. The composite beam is heated up by the CFRP heater to which the electric voltage is provided by the D.C. power supply.

Results and Discussion

The logarithmic decrement vs. the temperature of the specimen is shown in Fig. 6. At the room temperature the logarithmic decrement is less than 0.02. From about 45°C, the logarithmic decrement is increased as the temperature of the specimen increases. At 70°C, the logarithmic decrement reaches to 0.45. This value is more 20 times larger than the one at the room temperature.

The natural frequency of the specimen vs. the temperature of the specimen is also shown in Fig. 6. At the room temperature, the natural frequency is around 33Hz. From 45°C, the natural frequency is decreased as the temperature increases. The reason of this phenomenon is that when the damping property of constrained layer system is increased, not only the loss shear modulus, but also the shear deformation of the constrained layer are increased as a result of decreasing the storage shear modulus. From this result, the composite beam which has suitable dynamic properties can be produced by controlling the temperature of the specimen by using the CFRP heater.

Fig 5: Experiment set-up of free vibration test by using CFRP heater

Fig 6: Logarithmic decrement and natural frequency vs. temperature of composite beam specimen by using CFRP heater

Experiments in a thermostatic chamber

The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 7. A specimen having a strain gage is tested in a thermostatic chamber. In this experiment, the composite beam is heated up by the thermostatic chamber where the desirable temperature is controlled. The composite beam is supported under the clamped-free condition and the similar experiment is taken by free vibration test. The free vibration test is performed by a wire cut method, because of the restriction of the experimental set-up. The strain response at the fixed end is measured by the strain gage. The strain response is recorded by the FFT analyzer and converted to the vibration deflection response at the free end of the composite beam by using the beam theory.

Results and Discussion

The logarithmic decrement vs. the temperature of the specimen is plotted in Fig. 8. From this figure, it is found that the change of the logarithmic decrement is almost the same as the former case using the CFRP heater. But, the rate of the increment in this case is a little smaller than the one in the case using the CFRP heater. This may be supposed due to the reason that when the CFRP heater is used, the surface temperature of the specimen is a little different from the internal temperature of the specimen. Especially, over 50°C, the surface of the specimen is cooled by the room atmosphere. Thus the internal temperature of the specimen would be higher than the surface temperature. The damping property of the composite beam involving the SMP film depends on the visco-elastic property of the SMP. Therefore, it is important to recognize the internal temperature of the composite beam.

Fig 7: Experimental set-up of free vibration test by using thermostatic chamber

Fig 8: Logarithmic decrement vs. the temperature of composite beam specimen in thermostatic chamber

ANALYSIS

Ross-Kerwin-Ungar Analysis

Ross-Kerwin-Ungar analysis is used in order to predict the logarithmic decrement of the composite beam [6]. This RKU analysis has been developed for a three layer system. It is usually used to handle both extensional and shear types of treatment.

The flexural rigidity, EI^* , of the three-layer system shown in Fig. 9 is

$$\begin{aligned}
 EI^* = & E_1^* \frac{H_1^3}{12} + E_2^* \frac{H_2^3}{12} + E_3^* \frac{H_3^3}{12} - E_2^* \frac{H_2^2}{12} \left(\frac{H_{31} - D^*}{1 + g^*} \right) \\
 & + E_1^* H_1 D^{*2} + E_2^* H_2 (H_{21} - D^*)^2 + E_3^* H_3 (H_{31} - D^*)^2 \\
 & - \left[\frac{E_2^* H_2}{2} (H_{21} - D^*)^2 + E_3^* H_3 (H_{31} - D^*) \right] \left(\frac{H_{31} - D^*}{1 + g^*} \right)
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where,

$$D^* = \frac{E_2^* H_2 \left(H_{21} - \frac{H_{31}}{2} \right) + g^* (E_2^* H_2 H_{21} + E_3^* H_3 H_{31})}{\left(E_1^* H_1 + \frac{E_2^* H_2}{2} \right) + g^* (E_1^* H_1 + E_2^* H_2 + E_3^* H_3)}$$

$$H_{31} = \frac{(H_1 + H_3)}{2} + H_3, \quad H_{21} = \frac{(H_1 + H_2)}{2}, \quad g^* = \frac{G_2^*}{E_3^* H_3 H_2 p^2}, \quad p = \frac{\xi_n}{L},$$

Fig. 9: Composite beam model with shape memory polymer film

and E^* is the Young's modulus of elasticity, G^* is the shear modulus, I is the second moment of area, H is the thickness and ξ_n is the n th eigenvalue. Subscript 1 refers to the base structure, subscript 2 to the damping layer, subscript 3 to the constraining layer, and no subscript refers to the composite system. D is the distance from the neutral axis of the three layer system to that of the base structure. The logarithmic decrement is calculated from the imaginary part and the real part of flexural rigidity.

Results and Discussions

Fig. 10 shows a comparison of the experimental logarithmic decrement and the calculated ones. In this calculation, $H_1=H_3=0.4\text{mm}$, $H_2=0.2\text{mm}$, $\xi_n=22.373$ and $L=200\text{mm}$ were used. From this figure, it is found that the calculated value shows good agreement with the experimental value except that the calculated value is shifted to slightly lower region. The reason is explained as follows; any kind of chemical reactions are not considered in the analysis, and it is assumed that the composite beam consists of the completely separated the three layer system. However, actually, the chemical reaction might take place between the matrix resin for the prepreg sheet and the SMP film at the higher molding temperature. Thus, it is supposed that the interface between the prepreg sheet and the SMP film is not clearly distinct.

Fig 10: Comparison of experimental and calculated logarithmic decrements

CONCLUSION

It has been shown that the damping property of the CF/GF hybrid composite beam including shape memory polymer can be changed by controlling the temperature of the composite beam with the CFRP heater. The results obtained here are summarized as follows;

- 1) The CFRP laminate has a thermal capability which is enough to heat up the composite beam. CFRP [$\pm 45^\circ$] laminate is adopted to obtain the isotropy in electrical resistance.
- 2) The saturated temperatures of the composite beam are increased as increasing electric voltages applied to the CFRP heater. Increasing applied electric voltages, the specimen is heated faster.

- 3) The composite beam possessing a suitable damping property can be produced by controlling the temperature of the specimen by using the CFRP heater.
- 4) The damping property of the composite beam can be explained by Ross-Kerwin-Ungar analysis.

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